

TREATMENT OF VASOMOTOR RHINITIS WITH HIGH-ENERGY LASER IN AN OUTPATIENT CONDITION

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Abstract. The results of using the author's method for treating vasomotor rhinitis using a high-energy semiconductor laser for vasotomy of the inferior and middle turbinates are described. All operations were performed on an outpatient basis. Various versions of contact laser vasotomies were performed in 1620 patients with neurovegetative and 154 patients with allergic forms of chronic vasomotor rhinitis. The effectiveness of treatment 1 month after the intervention ranged from 92 to 97%. Persistent restoration of nasal breathing in the allergic form of the disease was observed in 126 people.

Keywords: ATKUS-15 laser, turbinates, vasotomy, efficiency.

INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, there has been a steady increase in the incidence of diseases of the nasal cavity and paranasal sinuses, due to deteriorating environmental conditions, an increase in the number of respiratory allergens and viral diseases, and a progressive decrease in local and general immunity in the population. Chronic vasomotor rhinitis (VR) occupies one of the leading places in the structure of diseases of the upper respiratory tract and is of great medical and social importance. According to epidemiological studies, about 20% of the population suffers from chronic rhinitis, and up to 40% of people periodically report the presence of certain symptoms of this disease. Persistent or periodic difficulty in nasal breathing, rhinorrhea and dependence on decongestants significantly reduce the quality of life of patients, worsens their psycho-emotional state, and limits social activity. Over time, VR contributes to the development of chronic inflammatory diseases of the paranasal sinuses, middle ear, pharynx and larynx [1-3].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Conservative methods of treatment of VR are not always are effective. The increasing incidence of neurovegetative and allergic forms of VR encourages otolaryngologists to search for ways to treat them. The development of new technologies and their application in rhinology has made it possible to optimize surgical procedures for a number of diseases of the nasal cavity, reduce the rehabilitation time for patients and perform surgical interventions on an

outpatient basis [2]. The use of a low-power, high-energy laser is the most promising method for treating various forms of VR, especially with contact exposure, which avoids the formation of an area of extensive necrosis, which has a positive effect on the healing time of the laser wound.

We have developed and introduced into the clinic methods of treating patients with VR using a high-energy semiconductor laser ATKUS-15 with a wavelength of $0.81\pm 0.03\ \mu\text{m}$ and assessed the clinical effectiveness of the proposed options for laser vasotomy of the inferior and middle turbinates in the complex treatment of various forms chronic VR.

1620 people suffered from the neurovegetative form of this disease – 91.3% of the total number of those observed. In 8.7% of cases, the allergic form of VR was diagnosed - 154 observations (including the persistent form - 112 cases, intermittent form - 42 cases). 77.5% of patients used vasoconstrictor drops for a long time, 29% of patients had previously attempted to treat VR using conservative and surgical methods, but without a long-term positive effect.

Indications for laser vasotomy of the inferior and middle turbinates were neurovegetative and allergic forms of VR; contraindications were deviated nasal septum, exacerbations of chronic diseases of the ENT organs, acute infectious diseases, diseases associated with blood coagulation disorders, hypertensive disease, oncological and oncohematological pathology, pregnancy and menstruation.

Laser coagulation of the mucous membrane of the inferior turbinates from the posterior end to the anterior in the form of two parallel grooves (in continuous mode) and points (in pulsed mode) was performed in 1336 and 285 patients, respectively. The effectiveness of the operation after 1 month was 97 and 95%. Contact laser coagulation of the mucous membrane and cavernous venous plexuses of the inferior and middle turbinates by applying pinholes and well-cuts in a continuous mode was performed in 53 and 41 patients, respectively. Effectiveness of operations after 1 month was 96 and 93%.

Laser tunnel contact coagulation of the cavernous venous plexuses of the inferior and middle turbinates and partial laser resection of the free edge of the inferior turbinate were performed in 32 and 27 patients, respectively. Efficiency of operations after 1 month was 92 and 93%.

In patients with an allergic form of VR, persistent restoration of nasal breathing was noted in 82% of cases. In the postoperative period, all these patients received inhalation of topical intranasal glucocorticosteroids. During

the year, in 5% of cases, representatives of this group were found to have relative difficulty in nasal breathing.

CONCLUSION

Thus, various versions of contact laser vasotomies of the inferior and middle turbinates were performed in 1620 patients with neurovegetative and in 154 patients with allergic forms of chronic VR. The effectiveness of the described interventions 1 month after their implementation ranged from 92 to 97%. Persistent restoration of nasal breathing in the allergic form of BP was observed in 126 people. Surgical interventions performed in an outpatient setting eliminated the need for hospitalization of this group of patients in an otorhinolaryngological hospital, and an analysis of the treatment results showed the high efficiency of the proposed methods of laser vasotomies of the inferior and middle turbinates

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